

Consumers' Intention to adopt Online Food Delivery Apps in Bangladesh: An Empirical Analysis

Samiya Bint Halim

Abstract

This study's aim was to explain the factors affecting consumers' intention to adopt online food delivery (OFD) apps in Bangladesh. In doing so, the author developed a research model by integrating the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model and innovation resistance theory. This quantitative study was conducted by collecting data from 256 respondents and those data were analyzed using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). In this research, the author found that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions have positive and significant effect on consumers' intent to adopt OFD apps, while adoption barriers had a negative influence upon consumers' behavioral intention. Several inferences for theory and management have been made on these findings.

IJSB

Accepted 17 January 2023
Published 18 January 2023
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7546091

Keywords: *Online Food Delivery (OFD), Intention to Adopt, UTAUT, Innovation Resistance Theory, PLS-SEM.*

About Author (s)

Samiya Bint Halim, Lecturer, Department of Business Administration, Bangladesh Army University of Science and Technology, Saidpur, Bangladesh.

1.Introduction

In recent years, the role of information/digital technologies in shaping and revolutionizing the retail/restaurant sector has been paramount, causing a notable surge in the use of digital platforms to buy/sell products/services by the consumers and marketers alike (Loureiro et al., 2020). This trend is popularly known as e-commerce (Kazandzhieva & Santana, 2019). The speedy intensification of e-commerce has generated several novel kinds of businesses. Online food delivery (OFD) platforms or apps are one of such segments of retail e-commerce through which consumers can place their food orders straightaway from their neighboring restaurants or restaurant mediators using mobile apps or other online platforms to have their desired foods delivered at a particular address or their doorstep (Ali et al., 2020). These online food delivery platforms allow customers to identify desired restaurants, to choose obtainable foodstuffs, and to provide a delivery location to order foods through online food delivery (OFD) options/services or restaurant websites (Ali et al., 2020). In recent times, the proliferation of digital platforms and rapid utilization of Smartphones have resulted in the commencement of a number of online food delivery startups, such as Food Panda, Pathao Food, Shohoz Food, and Hungry Naki, to name a few. Considering the widespread use of online food delivery (OFD) apps, several scholars have identified numerous positive factors that influence consumers to adopt OFD apps. For instance, Ali et al. (2020) found that optimism and innovativeness are significant positive reasons for accepting online food delivery apps (Ali et al., 2020), while Khandelwal & Singh (2020) combined “Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology” (UTAUT) as well as diffusion of innovation theory to ascertain consumer attitude toward adoption of online food ordering apps. They noted that effort expectancy, performance expectancy, perceived social norms, perceived compatibility, and perceived relative advantage (PRA) are substantial favorable predictors of consumers’ positive attitude and intention to adopt online food delivery apps. However, although several studies in the past explored why consumers adopt online food delivery apps (Bappy et al., 2021), those studies are mostly dominated by western cultures or countries that are rich in hospitality sector. This study will consider Bangladesh as research context considering the growing importance of restaurant/OFD sector in Bangladesh (Bappy & Samiya, 2018), which, however, differs significantly from the western counterparts in terms of culture, demographics, economic contribution of tourism sectors, and digital penetration rate. Thus, findings from past studies from western contexts need to be revalidated from Bangladeshi perspective as well. Besides, it has been witnessed that past studies have mostly focused on the positive factors that have an effect on OFD acceptance intentions (-hawari & Mouakket, 2012; Huang et al., 2013; Ku & Chen, 2015), whereas the barriers to the acceptance intentions of online food delivery technologies have hardly been investigated (Lama et al., 2019), particularly in developing country context. Although Bangladesh is a developing economy, internet penetration in the country is slow quite low (31.5 percent, as of April 2022) compared to other western/Southeast Asian economies (Data Portal, 2022). Thus, researchers believe that researchers should investigate both the positive factors and the barriers to adopt OFD apps in an integrated model to provide a holistic insights regarding Bangladeshi OFD apps adoption intention. In light of the aforementioned discussions, the researcher aims to examine the predictors of consumers’ OFD apps adoption intention based on UTAUT model and innovation resistance theory. In doing so, this study determined the relative influence of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, social influence on OFD apps adoption intention. Furthermore, the study ascertained the influence of barriers (usage barrier, value barrier, risk barrier, tradition barrier, and image barrier) on OFD apps adoption intention. In this way, the researcher has made several contributions through this study. First, the study validates and integrates UTAUT model and IRT to enhance our understanding of OFD apps adoption intentions. Second, the research believes that as a study on OFD apps adoption intentions is limited in Bangladeshi

context, this research has fulfilled the extant contextual and knowledge gap in the extant literature.

2. Literature Review:

2.1 Theoretical Foundation

This study has employed unified theory of acceptance and usage of technology (UTAUT) model (Venkatesh et al., 2003) to extract the positive reasons for OFD apps adoption intentions. According to UTAUT model, those reasons can be performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, and social influence (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Besides, the barriers of accepting OFD technology/apps have been extracted from innovation resistance theory (IRT) (Kaur et al., 2020). Those barriers include usage barrier, value barrier, risk barrier, tradition barrier, and image barrier (Himel et al., 2021). Subsequently, the constructs derived from these two theories have been incorporated in a holistic model to predict consumers' behavioral intention toward accepting OFD apps. In the past, these two theories were applied to understand users' intention to adopt novel technologies in numerous fields. Besides, the predictive utility of these two models is well recognized in the extant literature. Thus, the use of these two theories seems logical in this study.

2.2 Hypotheses Development

2.2.1 Performance Expectancy (PE) and Intention:

Performance Expectancy (PE), a vital variable of UTAUT model, indicates how much users acknowledge utilizing a technological platform or information system is going to assist in the implementation of certain tasks (Venkatesh et al., 2003). PE is similar to certain latent constructs, including "perceived usefulness" (Davis, 1989) and "relative advantage" (Moore & Benbasat, 1991), which were used in the technology acceptance model (TAM) and diffusion of innovation (DOI) theories respectively. The performance expectancy helps an individual to accomplish or gain in job performance (Venkatesh et al., 2012). In case of UTAUT model, PE is considered as one of the strongest predictors of intention (Agarwal & Prasad, 1998; Greener, 2022). According to several latest studies, PE has been constructively connected with the users' technology acceptance intention (Wang et al., 2012, Jang et al., 2016; Menash et al., 2020). Liang et al., (2018) provided empirical facts that greater PE can build favorable enthusiasm to acknowledge innovative technologies. Since, online food delivery (OFD) apps are considered an innovative digital technological solution, it may be hypothesized that:

H1: Higher performance expectancy of OFD apps will lead to greater intention to use the OFD apps.

2.2.2 Effort Expectancy (EE) and Intention

Effort Expectancy (EE) signifies the level to which users consider using certain innovations to be straightforward and hassle-free (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Past studies found that EE assertively affects users' persistence usage intention of using mobile apps (Kang, 2014; Fang and Fang, 2016). Similarly, scholars also provided evidence on the fact that EE helps internet users to boost up performance expectancy on the way to the adoption intention of an innovative technology (Chaouali et al., 2016). Therefore, it can be hypothesized:

H2: Higher effort expectancy of OFD apps will lead to greater intention to use the OFD apps.

2.2.3 Facilitating Conditions and Intention

Facilitating conditions (FC) refers to distinct perceptions of the availability of technological resources (i.e., knowledge, assets, and opportunities), the availability of which will facilitate technological adoption behavior; and the absence of which will create certain obstacles to using a technology (Venkatesh et al. 2003). In the context of present study, facilitating conditions

include smartphones, mobile apps, internet connections that will support the consumers in their food ordering. In several recent studies that facilitating conditions and behavioral intentions are positively correlated (Shankar et al., 2022 and Chakraborty et al., 2022). Considering these pieces of evidence, it can be assumed:

H3: Higher facilitating conditions are more likely to increase consumers' intention to use the OFD apps.

2.2.4 Social Influence and Intention

Social norms are understood as social pressures exerted by the surrounding environment, which shapes individuals' intention to perform a particular action (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Social influence comes from significant people/groups that have significant roles in consumer decision makings (Venkatesh et al., 2012). In technology acceptance literature, social influences are deemed as crucial predictor of individuals' intention to accept innovations (Joe et al., 2020). People may feel discomfort in their acceptance or adoption of a novel technological invention (such as, OFD apps) since the effectiveness of such technological invention may remain uncertain under most circumstances. Hence, people/consumers are likely to take the opinion of other individuals with regard to decisions to adopt new technological innovation. Past empirical studies found that social influence can positively and significantly predict technology users' behavioral intention (Nysveen et al., 2005; Venkatesh et al., 2012; Joe et al., 2020). On that note, it may be hypothesized:

H4: Positive social influence will lead to greater intention to use the OFD apps.

2.2.5 Barriers and Intention

As per Ram and Sheth (1989), the acceptance of latest innovations is likely to be abandoned or deferred as a consequence of numerous functional and psychological barriers. In light of innovation resistance theory (Himel et al., 2021), the functional barriers related to innovation (i.e., apps) adoption intention include usage barriers, value barriers, and risk barriers (Kaur et al., 2020). Besides, Laukkanen (2016) argued that the psychological barriers connected to innovative technology adoption may be tradition barriers (having technology anxiety, for example) and image barriers (for instance, forming an unfavorable image that the technological usage is complex). Several recent studies found that these barriers may create obstacles to the adoption of innovation; as a result consumers' propensity to accept a technological innovation reduces (Laukkanen, 2016; Kaur et al., 2020; Himel et al., 2021). Hence, the authors can hypothesize:

H5: Higher level of adoption barriers will lead to lower intention to use the OFD apps.

Based on aforementioned hypotheses, the researcher has developed a research model, which has been demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

3. Research Methodology:

3.1. Research Design

This is a quantitative study which employed a cross sectional survey to collect responses from the respondents. The reason for using cross sectional survey is that this survey technique requires low cost and provides data in a specific period (Malhotra & Das, 2016). Besides, unlike longitudinal study, participants in a cross sectional study are less likely to refuse to participate in the research (Malhotra & Das, 2016).

3.2. Survey Item, Measurement, and Scaling

In this research, the researcher employed five reflective exogenous constructs (performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, social influence, and barriers), one reflective endogenous construct (intention to adopt OFD apps) as depicted in Figure 1. The latent constructs, such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, and social influence were measured with four indicators, which were adapted from Izzati (2020), while the construct “barriers to acceptance were measured using six indicators adapted from Himel et al. (2021). Besides, the exogenous construct “intention to adopt” was evaluated using four indicators, which were drawn from Himel et al. (2021). In this study, the wordings of the adapted scale items were customized keeping this paper’s context in view. All the indicators of the latent variables were measured with five point Likert scale with anchors ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. All the 25 scale items are depicted in Appendix 1.

3.3 Questionnaire Design, Data Collection, Pre and Pilot Test

This study has employed a semi-structured questionnaire to capture data from the participants. The survey instrument was prepared in English and Bangla to advocate the smooth understanding of the participants. Initially, the questionnaire was pretested using protocol method with 12 samples to confirm that the survey items’ phrasing and arrangements are satisfactory. Furthermore, a pilot study was carried out using 26 respondents to endorse that the scales are reliable enough to perform the full-scale research project. Previously,

scholars argued that a sample size of 12 respondents is enough for pre-testing while a sample size range from 10 to 30 respondents are sufficient for a pilot test (Mumtaz et al., 2017; Popy & Bappy, 2020). Considering these thresholds, the authors of this study believe that the sample size chosen for pre-testing and pilot testing are adequate.

3.4. Sampling Plan

The researcher used convenient sampling technique to capture data from 256 respondents from Dhaka, Bangladesh. Convenient sampling was preferred in this paper because scholars argue that random sample selection is a challenging task in the social science studies (Krause, 2019). Besides, the study's authors could not gather fitting sampling frame as the companies were unwilling to provide the identities of the list of employees, which encouraged the researchers to employ a non-probability sampling technique named convenient sampling. Moreover, researchers, such as Mumtaz et al. (2017) and Ahmed Bappy et al. (2020), opined that non-probability sampling provides satisfactory results if the researchers aim to test theoretical models without making broad generalizations. The current study focuses on validating a research model developed based on prior theoretical evidence. Therefore, the adoption of non-probability sampling in this paper is rational. While determining sample size, the authors relied upon power analysis using G*power because recent academics mentioned that sample size in social science studies should be determined utilizing power analysis (Faul et al., 2009; Mumtaz et al., 2017). G*power analysis reveals that a minimum sample size of 77 would be sufficient for a research model with 3 predictors, medium effect size of .15, 80% power, and 5% significance level (Faul et al., 2009). The researchers distributed the questionnaire to 1000 respondents both online and offline. After screening the questionnaire, several straight-liners, missing responses, unfulfilled questionnaire were identified. Ultimately, the researchers retained 256 valid questionnaires for final data collection. Therefore, this study's sample size was 256 respondents, which surpassed the least sample size requirements provided by Kline (2015) and Faul et al. (2009).

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques and Tools

The researchers applied Microsoft Excel 2010 for data input and screening. In addition, SPSS version 23 was used to summarize the respondents' demographic profile. Besides, this study evaluated the measurement and structural model using partial least square-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) technique. Smart-PLS version 3 has been employed to perform PLS-SEM analysis. The reason for choosing PLS-SEM over covariance based SEM is that PLS-SEM is a prediction oriented statistical technique that works well even with non-normal data and smaller sample size (Hair et al., 2021). This study mainly predicts based on consumers' intention to adopt OFD apps in light of several predictors. Consequently, owing to its predictive utility, the application of PLS-SEM using Smart-PLS is justified in this research. Furthermore, the motive behind adopting Smart-PLS instead of AMOS was that Smart-PLS provides the results of complex measurement model and structural model simultaneously (Ahmed Bappy et al., 2020).

4. Findings

This study used five reflective exogenous constructs and one reflective endogenous construct. In the first place, the author ascertained the reliability and validity of the scales of the measurement model. Scale reliability was determined through composite reliability (CR) scores (Hair et al., 2021). As shown in Table 1, CR values of all the constructs were beyond the threshold level of .7, indicating acceptable reliability (Malhotra & Das, 2016). Besides, the researcher measured the convergent validity on the basis of average variance extracted (AVE) scores and item loadings (Hair et al., 2021). As can be seen in the Table 1, all the item loadings

were higher than the cutoff point of .70 and AVE scores of all the constructs were above the recommended level of .5, demonstrating sufficient convergent validity (Malhotra & Das, 2016).

Table 1: Measurement Model Evaluation

Constructs	Item Code	Item Loading	AVE	CR
Performance Expectancy	PE1	0.756	0.633	0.873
	PE2	0.742		
	PE3	0.836		
	PE4	0.844		
Effort Expectancy	EE1	0.732	0.617	0.865
	EE2	0.752		
	EE3	0.776		
	EE4	0.874		
Facilitating Conditions	FC1	0.766	0.696	0.901
	FC2	0.911		
	FC3	0.876		
	FC4	0.774		
Social Influence	SI1	0.736	0.664	0.887
	SI2	0.882		
	SI3	0.876		
	SI4	0.755		
Barriers	Value Barrier	0.742	0.562	0.856
	Risk Barrier	0.733		
	Image Barrier	0.779		
	Usage Barrier	0.758		
	Tradition Barrier	0.737		
Intention to Adopt OFD	INT1	0.869	0.605	0.820
	INT2	0.719		
	INT3	0.737		

Furthermore, the discriminant validity of the scales was assessed based on heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio, which is one of the contemporary methods of ascertaining discriminant validity. As shown in the Table 2, HTMT scores of all the constructs were below .80, which indicates that the each construct differs from the other construct conceptually (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 2: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	INT	Barriers	PE	EE	FC	SI
INT						
Barriers	0.335					
PE	0.685	0.417				
EE	0.644	0.256	0.645			
FC	0.642	0.354	0.613	0.636		
SI	0.657	0.134	0.621	0.711	0.512	

Subsequently, the structural model was evaluated to test this study's hypotheses. In this study, the R square was found to be .47, indicating moderate degree of explanatory power of the research model. The VIF values of all the constructs were lower than 3.3, signifying no multicollinearity issues.

Table 3: Structural Model Evaluation

Hypotheses	Paths	Std Beta	Std Error	T values	Decisions
H1	PE--> INT	0.236	0.051	4.627*	Supported
H2	EE-->INT	0.214	0.072	2.972*	Supported
H3	FC--> INT	0.322	0.069	4.667*	Supported
H4	SI--> INT	0.266	0.052	5.115*	Supported
H5	Barriers--> INT	-0.227	0.064	-3.547*	Supported

Note: *P value <0.05

The author of this study hypothesized that higher performance expectancy of OFD apps will lead to greater intention to use the OFD apps. As demonstrated in the Table 3, the relationship between performance expectancy and intention was found to be positive and significant ($\beta=0.236$, $T= 4.627$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, H1 was supported. Moreover, the author also assumed that higher effort expectancy of OFD apps will lead to greater intention to use the OFD apps. As can be seen in the Table 3, the path from effort expectancy (EE) and intention (INT) was positive and substantial ($\beta=0.214$, $T= 2.972$, $p < 0.05$). Consequently, H2 was accepted. Besides, it was postulated that higher facilitating conditions are more likely to increase consumers' intention to use the OFD apps. It has been shown in the Table 3 that the relationship from facilitating condition (FC) and intention to use OFD apps (INT) was positive and significant ($\beta=0.322$, $T= 4.667$, $p < 0.05$). For this reason, H3 was supported. Furthermore, it was proposed that positive social influence will lead to greater intention to use the OFD apps. Table 3 reveals that the connection between social influence (SI) and intention to use OFD apps (INT) was favorable and substantial ($\beta=0.266$, $T= 5.115$, $p < 0.05$). As a consequence, H4 was accepted. Finally, the researcher hypothesized that higher level of adoption barriers will lead to lower intention to use the OFD apps. Table 3 shows that the path from barriers to intention was negative and significant, indicating the relationship between barriers and intention was inversely proportional ($\beta= -0.227$, $T= -3.547$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, H5 was supported in this study.

6. Discussion & Implications

This study confirms that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, social influence and barriers are the predictors of consumer's intention to use OFD apps. Firstly, performance expectancy and consumer's intention to use OFD apps are positively correlated. This output corroborates the results of past studies conducted by Palau-Saumell et al. (2019) and Menash et al. (2020). This means that food consumers will have the willingness to use the apps when they feel the efficiency of OFD apps such as less time, fast transaction procedures, various buying options. This study also found that effort expectancy of OFD apps has positive influence on consumer's intention. Similar relationships were previously directed by Kang (2014) and Chaouali et al. (2016). This indicates if all other things remain constant, users' willingness to use OFD apps will increase when they perceive the use of OFD apps to be easy and effortless. For this reason, OFD service providers should design their apps in an easy and user friendly manner. This research also showed facilitating conditions has positive influence on consumers' intention to adopt OFD apps. This result matches with the findings demonstrated by Shankar et al. (2022) and Chakraborty et al. (2022). This signifies that all else being equal, users are likely to use OFD apps when they have the necessary resources such as knowledge, gadgets, internet connection, time and many more. Therefore OFD service providers should provide their customers with the knowledge that are essential to accept the OFD apps for buying foods. This study also suggested that social influence has a strong positive influence on consumers' intention to adopt OFD apps. This consequence matches with the findings demonstrated by Venkatesh et al. (2012) and Joe et al. (2020). In today's world people are too much active on social media, so there is an immense need to endorse their OFD apps to popular faces of social media. Popular social influencers on social media should provide some

discounts or PR gifts so that they promote the brands to their family members, friends, and colleagues and so on. This helps to stimulate the users for further usage of OFD apps. This research demonstrated that barriers are negatively correlated to consumer's intention to use OFD apps. These verdicts were earlier directed by Himel et al. (2021). These several types of barriers such as usage barriers, value barriers, and risk barriers are the key to demotivate the OFD clients. Many customers think that there were several obstacles not to use these OFD apps for instance: the risk of transaction, not to have the required knowledge or habit to use the apps, the unnecessary harassment by the providers or deliveryman, residing in a remote area and many more. For this reason, OFD service providers should eradicate these barriers from the minds of the customers.

7. Conclusion, Limitations and Future Research Scopes

This study makes several contributions to the existing literature on online food delivery services. First, the study integrated UTAUT model and innovation resistance theory to examine both the positive and negative determinants of consumers' behavioral intention to use OFD apps. The explanatory and predictive power of the research model has been enhanced due to this theoretical integration. Second, this study contributes to the existing knowledge by focusing on one of the rarely studied research areas like online food delivery services of Bangladesh. However, the study is not without limitations. This study used only five determinants of consumers' behavioral intention to use OFD apps. In future, scholars can add more variables, such as perceived enjoyment or perceived experience, in their model to enhance its predictive utility. Besides, a cross cultural study might be conducted to examine if usage intention varies among the cultures. Despite having these limitations, it may be argued that this study will remain a benchmark for the scholars who have a desire to extend the literature on consumer behavior in online food delivery sectors.

References:

- Agarwal, R., & Prasad, J. (1998). A conceptual and operational definition of information technology. *Information Systems Research*, 9, 204–215.
- Ahmed Bappy, T., Shariful Haque, S. M., Bint Halim, S., & Nazmul Hossai, M. (2020). Predicting Passengers' Uber Adoption Behaviour: Evidence from Bangladesh. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*
- Al-hawari, M.A. & Mouakket, S. (2012). Do offline factors trigger customers' appetite for online continual usage?: A study of online reservation in the airline industry. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 24(4) 640-645.
- Ali, S., Khalid, N., Javed, H. M. U., & Islam, D. Md. Z. (2020). Consumer Adoption of Online Food Delivery Ordering (OFDO) Services in Pakistan: The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic Situation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 10. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7010010>
- Asimakopoulos, G., Hernández, V., & Peña Miguel, J. (2019). Entrepreneurial intention of engineering students: The role of social norms and entrepreneurial self-efficacy. *Sustainability*, 11(16), 4314.
- Bai, B., Law, R. & Wen, I. (2008). The impact of website quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intentions: Evidence from Chinese online visitors. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27, 391-402.
- Bappy, T. A., & Bint Halim, S. (2018). The Impact of Service Quality Dimensions on Visitors' Satisfaction towards the Theme Parks of Bangladesh: An Empirical Study on Fantasy Kingdom Based on SERVQUAL Model. *AIUB Journal of Business and Economics*, 15(1), 61-81.
- Bappy, T. A., Avi, M., & Rahman, A. (2021). Technological Innovation Application in the Tourism and Hospitality Industry of Bangladesh. In *Technology Application in the Tourism and Hospitality Industry of Bangladesh* (pp. 63-77). Springer, Singapore.
- Chakraborty, D., Bhatnagar, S. B., Biswas, W., & Khatua, A. K. (2022). What drives people to adopt grocery apps? The moderating role of household size. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 22785337221091640.)
- Chaouali, W., Yahia, I. B., & Souiden, N. (2016). The interplay of counter-conformity motivation, social influence, and trust in customers' intention to adopt Internet banking services: The case of an emerging country. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 28, 209-218.

- Chung, N., Lee, H., Lee, S.J. & Koo, C. (2015). The influence of tourism website on tourists' behavior to determine destination selection: a case study of creative economy in Korea. *Technology Forecasting and Social Change*, 96, 130-143
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 319-340.
- Eweoya, I., Okuboyejo, S. R., & Agomuo, K. (2016). The adoption of E-tourism: An empirical investigation.
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Buchner, A., & Lang, A. G. (2009). Statistical power analyses using G* Power 3.1: Tests for correlation and regression analyses. *Behavior research methods*, 41(4), 1149-1160.
- Greener, S. (2022). Digging for acceptance theory. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(4), 587-588.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2021). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage publications.
- Hamid, R. A., Albahri, A. S., Alwan, J. K., Al-Qaysi, Z. T., Albahri, O. S., Zaidan, A. A., ... & Zaidan, B. B. (2021). How smart is e-tourism? A systematic review of smart tourism recommendation system applying data management. *Computer Science Review*, 39, 100337.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 43(1), 115-135.
- Himel, M.T.A., Ashraf, S., Bappy, T.A., Abir, M.T., Morshed, M.K. and Hossain, M.N. (2021), "Users' attitude and intention to use mobile financial services in Bangladesh: an empirical study", *South Asian Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 72-96. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJM-02-2021-0015>
[https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-bangladesh#:~:text=Bangladesh's%20internet%20penetration%20rate%20stood,percent\)%20between%202021%20and%202022.](https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-bangladesh#:~:text=Bangladesh's%20internet%20penetration%20rate%20stood,percent)%20between%202021%20and%202022.)
- Huang, Y., Backman, S.J., Backman, K.F. & Moore, D. (2013). Exploring user acceptance of 3D virtual worlds in travel and tourism marketing. *Tourism Management*, 36, 490-501.
- Izzati, B. M. (2020). Analysis of customer behavior in mobile food ordering application using UTAUT model (case study: GoFood application). *International Journal of Innovation in Enterprise System*, 4(01), 23-34.
- Joe, S., Kim, J. (Sunny), & Zemke, D. M. V. (2020). Effects of Social Influence and Perceived Enjoyment on Kiosk Acceptance: A Moderating Role of Gender. *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, 1-28. doi:10.1080/15256480.2020.17462
- Kang S. 'Factors influencing intention of mobile application use' *Int. J. Mob. Commun.* 2014;12(4):360-379.
- Kaur, P., Dhir, A., Singh, N., Sahu, G. and Almotairi, M. (2020), "An innovation resistance theory perspective on mobile payment", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 55, p. 102059.
- Kaur, P., Dhir, A., Singh, N., Sahu, G., & Almotairi, M. (2020). An innovation resistance theory perspective on mobile payment solutions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 55, 102059.
- Kazandzhieva, V., & Santana, H. (2019). E-tourism: Definition, development and conceptual framework. *Tourism: An International Interdisciplinary Journal*, 67(4), 332-350.
- Khandelwal, U., & Singh, T. P. (2022). An Empirical Study of Consumer Attitude Toward Adoption of Online Food Ordering App. *International Journal of E-Services and Mobile Applications (IJESMA)*, 14(1), 1-18. <http://doi.org/10.4018/IJESMA.285549>
- Kline, R. B. (2015). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. Guilford publications.
- Krueger, N.F.; Brazeal, D.V. Entrepreneurial Potential and Potential Entrepreneurs. *Entrep Theory Pract.* 1994, 18, 91-104
- Ku, E.C.S. & Chen, C. (2015). Cultivating traveler's revisit intention to e-tourism service: the moderating effect of website interactivity. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 34(5) 465-478
- Lama, S., Pradhan, S., & Shrestha, A. (2019). An e-tourism adoption model & its implications for tourism industry in Nepal. In *Information and communication technologies in tourism 2019* (pp. 291-303). Springer, Cham.
- Lama, S., Pradhan, S., & Shrestha, A. (2019). An e-tourism adoption model & its implications for tourism industry in Nepal. In *Information and communication technologies in tourism 2019* (pp. 291-303). Springer, Cham.
- Laukkanen, T. (2016), "Consumer adoption versus rejection decisions in seemingly similar service innovations: the case of the Internet and mobile banking", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 69 No. 7, pp. 2432-2439.
- Laukkanen, T. (2016), "Consumer adoption versus rejection decisions in seemingly similar service innovations: the case of the Internet and mobile banking", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 69, No. 7, pp. 2432-2439.
- Liang, X., Jin, Y. and Jiang, J. (2018). "Factors impacting consumers" sharing behaviour under sharing economy: A UTAUT-based model", *ICEB 2018 Proceedings*, Vol. 71. pp. 317-324.
- Loureiro, S. M. C., Guerreiro, J., & Ali, F. (2020). 20 years of research on virtual reality and augmented reality in tourism context: A text-mining approach. *Tourism management*, 77, 104028.
- Lu, J., Yu, C. S., & Liu, C. (2005). Facilitating conditions, wireless trust and adoption intention. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 46(1), 17-24.
- Malhotra, N.K. & Dash, S. (2016), *Marketing Research: An Applied Orientation*, 7th ed., Pearson India Education Services, Bengaluru.

- Moore, G. C., & Benbasat, I. (1991). Development of an instrument to measure the perceptions of adopting an information technology innovation. *Information Systems Research*, 2(3), 192–222. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2.3.192>
- Mumtaz, A. M., Ting, H., Ramayah, T., Chuah, F., & Cheah, J. H. (2017). Editorial, 'a review of the methodological misconceptions and guidelines related to the application of structural equation modelling: a Malaysian scenario'. *Journal of Applied Structural Equation Modeling*, 1(1), 1-13.
- Nysveen, H., Pedersen, P. E., Thorbjørnsen, H., & Berthon, P. (2005). Mobilizing the brand: The effects of mobile services on brand relationships and main channel use. *Journal of Service Research*, 7(3), 257–276. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670504271151>
- Oh, Sujin; Lehto, Xinran Y.; Park, Jungkun (2009). Travelers' Intent to Use Mobile Technologies as a Function of Effort and Performance Expectancy. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 18(8), 765–781
- Palau-Saumell, R., Forgas-Coll, S., Sánchez-García, J., & Robres, E. (2019). User acceptance of mobile apps for restaurants: An expanded and extended UTAUT-2. *Sustainability*, 11(4), 1210.
- Popy, N. N., & Bappy, T. A. (2020). Attitude toward social media reviews and restaurant visit intention: a Bangladeshi perspective. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*.
- Ram, S. and Sheth, J.N. (1989), "Consumer resistance to innovations: the marketing problem and its solutions", *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 05-14
- Rasli, M. A. M., Zulkefli, N. H., Salleh, N. S. A., Ghani, F. A., Razali, N. A., & Idris, R. S. N. R. (2020). Determinants of Behavioural Intention on Online Food Delivery (OFD) APPS: Extending UTAUT2 with Information Quality. *Global Business & Management Research*, 12(4).
- Ray A., Dhir A., Bala P.K., Kaur P. Why do people use food delivery apps (FDA)? A uses and gratification theory perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Elsevier Ltd.* 2019;51:221–230. (March)
- Ren, S., Kwon, S. D., & Cho, W. S. (2020). Online Food Delivery (OFD) services in Cambodia: A study of the factors influencing consumers' behavioral intentions to use.
- Saeed, S.; Yousafzai, S.Y.; Yani-De-Soriano, M.; Muffatto, M. The role of perceived university support in the formation of students' entrepreneurial intention. *J. Small Bus. Manag.* 2015, 53, 1127–1145
- San Martín, H., & Herrero, Á. (2012). Influence of the user's psychological factors on the online purchase intention in rural tourism: Integrating innovativeness to the UTAUT framework. *Tourism Management*, 33(2), 341–350.
- Shankar, A., Jebarajakirthy, C., Nayal, P., Maseeh, H. I., Kumar, A., & Sivapalan, A. (2022). Online food delivery: A systematic synthesis of literature and a framework development. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 104, 103240.
- Tam C., Oliveira T. 'Understanding the impact of m-banking on individual performance: DeLone& McLean and TTF perspective.' *Comput. Human Behav.* 2016;61:233–244.
- Thomas, A.; Passaro, R.; Scandurra, G. The Perception of the Contextual Factors as Predictor of Entrepreneurial Intent: Evidences from an Empirical Survey. *J. Enterp. Cult.* 2014, 22, 375–400
- Ukpabi, D. C., & Karjaluo, H. (2017). Consumers' acceptance of information and communications technology in tourism: A review. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(5), 618–644.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS quarterly*, 425-478.
- Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y. L., & Xu, X. (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of in- formation technology: Extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(1), 157–178.

Appendix 1: Measurement items

Constructs	Item Code	Item Description	Reference
Performance Expectancy (PE)	PE 1	I believe that OFD apps are useful for food ordering	Izzati (2020)
	PE 2	I feel that my productivity will enhance if I use OFD apps	
	PE 3	I believe that OFD apps will help me receive the ordered foods quickly	
	PE 4	I think that my chance to achieve the important things will enhance if I use OFD apps	
Effort Expectancy (EE)	EE1	I think it is easy for me to use the OFD apps	Izzati (2020)
	EE2	OFD apps are not complicated to use	
	EE3	I found that OFD apps' features & navigation systems are effortless	
	EE4	I found that the features of OFD apps are easy to understand	
Facilitating Conditions	FC 1	To use OFD apps, I have the necessary resources	Izzati (2020)
	FC 2	To use the OFD apps, I have the essential knowledge	
	FC 3	I have the necessary technologies to adopt the OFD apps	

	FC 4	I receive others' assistance when I want to use OFD apps	
Social Influence	SI 1	People important to me suggest me to use OFD apps for food ordering	Izzati (2020)
	SI 2	People who are influential to me think that I should utilize OFD apps for ordering foods	
	SI 3	I am highly influenced by the opinion of my friends and families when it comes to using OFD apps	
	SI 4	People whose opinion I respect believe that using OFD apps for ordering food is convenient	
Adoption Barriers	Value Barrier	OFD apps do not offer many advantages compared with other ways of ordering foods	Himel et al. (2021)
	Risk Barrier	I fear that while I am using an OFD app, I might type the information of the food, address or bill incorrectly	
	Image Barrier	I have such an image that an OFD apps are difficult to use	
	Usage Barrier	I believe learning and using an OFD app is a complicated process	
Intention to Adopt OFD apps	Tradition Barrier	Due to my lack of technical knowledge, I find it difficult to order food using an OFD app	Himel et al. (2021)
	INT 1	I would like to use OFD apps for ordering foods in the future	
	INT 2	I future, I have an intention to use OFD apps	
	INT 3	I have a willingness to use OFD apps in the next food order	

Cite this article:

Samiya Bint Halim (2023). Consumers' Intention to adopt Online Food Delivery Apps in Bangladesh: An Empirical Analysis. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 21(1), 1-12. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7546091>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/2071.pdf>

Published by

